

THE EFFECT OF LONG WORKING HOURS AND OVERTIME ON OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH FOR TEACHERS IN THE SPHERE OF TRANSLATION.

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Annotation: Since 1997, no subsequent meta-analysis examining the effects of long working hours on health or occupational Health has been conducted since 1997.

This paper aims to conduct a meta-analysis of studies after 1997 for comparison. In electronic databases, a total of 243 published records were extracted from electronic databases.

Keywords: physiological health; mental health; sleep disturbance; occupational injury; healthbehaviours; working class; occupational health.

Аннотация: с 1997 года не проводилось ни одного последующего метанаализа, изучающего влияние продолжительного рабочего дня на здоровье или гигиену труда. Эта статья направлена на проведение метаанализа исследований после 1997 года для сравнения в электронных базах данных из электронных баз данных было извлечено в общей сложности 243 опубликованных записи.

Ключевые слова: физиологическое здоровье; душевное здоровье; нарушение сна; производственная травма; поведение в отношении здоровья; рабочий класс; гигиена труда.

Annotatsiya: 1997 yildan beri uzoq ish soatlarining salomatlik yoki mehnat salomatligiga ta'sirini o'rganuvchi keyingi meta-tahlil 1997 yildan beri o'tkazilmagan. Ushbu maqola taqqoslash uchun 1997 yildan keyingi tadqiqotlarning meta-tahlilini o'tkazishga qaratilgan. Elektron ma'lumotlar bazalarida jami 243 ta nashr etilgan yozuvlar elektron ma'lumotlar bazalaridan olingan.

Kalit so'zlar: fiziologik salomatlik; ruhiy salomatlik; uyqu buzilishi; kasbiy shikastlanish; salomatlik xatti-harakatlari; ishchilar sinfi; mehnat salomatligi.

An average rate of odds ratios for long working hours and health was 1.245 (95% confident interval (CI): 1.195–1.298). The overall risk factor in the relationship with long working hours and occupational health was 1.245. The condition of related health was the highest odds ratio value (1.465, 95% CI: 1.332–1.611), and the condition of related health is the highest odds ratio value

(1.465, 95% CI: 1.332–1.611). In the scenario, the potential moderators were study method and cut-point for long working hours. The of factors affecting occupational health is important to safeguard employees through control of occupational diseases and accidents and to eliminate hazards that threaten the health of workers. Such studies are necessary in order to maintain the quality of work and working environments and to develop a society which ultimately achieves sustainable development [1] . Long working hours are a ubiquitous phenomenon amongst most organizations and companies where the length of time spending on work, comprising main tasks of job, related tasks, commuting, and travel, is too long and detrimental to the health of workers directly or indirectly [2]. Epidemiological studies have shown the negative effects of long working hours on the risks of cardiovascular diseases; chronic fatigue, stress; depressive state, anxiety, sleep quality, all-cause mortality, alcohol use and smoking; and self-perceived health, mental health status, hypertension, and health behaviours. Similar results have been found for long working hours by other studies, for instance, myocardial infarction, poor physical health and injuries, alcohol consumption, smoking, physical inactivity, and depression. Many studies have investigated the effects of different working hours on the occurrence of cardiovascular and cerebrovascular diseases. A U-shaped relationship between the risk of suffering from myocardial infarction and working hours for Japanese workers was found. Those working less than 7 h per day or more than 11 h per day were at greater risk of experiencing myocardial infarction than with those working 7 to 11 h. Researchers also found that workers in Europe, Japan, Korea, and China who work more than 50 h per week had an increased risk of cerebrocardiovascular diseases, myocardial infarction, and coronary heart disease. Long working hours have been a controversial issue starting from 1980s, when it was reported that a Japanese design engineer died of brain hemorrhage due to working 2600 h per year. Subsequently, the governments of Japan, Korea and Taiwan recognized that the number of deaths from overwork among workers was increasing. This phenomenon of ‘working to death’ was also reported to have occurred in many organizations and factories in China. Long working hours became a focal issue among Western countries, for examples, the United States, the United Kingdom, Canada, France and Germany. This interest in long working hours resulted in studies to investigate the impact of long working hours on the health of workers in a variety of industries, for various health symptoms, and for ranges of social status. In general, the findings were that long working hours have adverse effects on health. In spite of the

importance of long working hours, apart from the meta-analysis conducted by Sparks and Cooper discovering a slightly positive correlation between various health syndromes and long working hours, there has been no subsequent meta-analysis examining the effects of long working hours on health or occupational health. The issue of long working hours is of great importance in every society, and therefore, it is necessary to investigate the effects of long working hours on the health of workers to identify any changes in the severity of such effect after the previous study conducted in 1997. Further, few studies have addressed the effects of working class, i.e., collar colour occupations, on the association between long working hours and occupational health. It has been argued that occupation is a factor in health inequality among workers. Therefore, the influence of occupation on the association between long working hours and occupational health needs to be investigated. In this paper, a meta-analysis was conducted to synthesize the data from studies from 1998 to 2018 on the effects of working long hours on the occupational health of employees. The purpose here was to examine the relationship between the length of work hours and the occupational health of workers. Occupational Injury. Excessive working hours increase the risk of occupational injury. Studies on the effect of long working hours on occupational injury have shown that overtime working increased the risk of occupational injuries. Further, a study found that working 12 or more hours per day and 60 or more hours per week increased the risk of occupational injury. Reported an increase in occupational injuries [5] when working more than 70 h per week compared to those working 41 to 69 h per week.

According to several studies and reports, teaching is one of the most stressful jobs in the country [3]. The American Federation of Teachers' 2017 Educator Quality of Work Life Survey found that 61 percent of teachers said their jobs were always or often stressful more than double the rate of non-teaching working adults and 58 percent said they had poor mental health due to stress levels. Your mental health isn't only important to you, teacher wellness is also linked to stability in schools and student achievement [4].

Conclusions: Teachers are often on their feet all day and spend a lot of time moving around the classroom. It may not seem like much, but you're actually releasing a lot of energy through that constant movement. If your school has gone virtual, you may be sitting a lot more. Set a timer to remind yourself to get up, even if it's just for a 30-second stretch or walk around your house or apartment. If you want more consistent movement, think about using a yoga ball for a chair, get a standing desk, or buy a mini exercise bike for under your desk.

The resolution demonstrated that worker working long hours were vulnerable to suffering from diversiform types of occupational health problem.

References:

1. WHO. Occupational Health: A Manual for Primary Health Care Workers; WHO: Geneva, Switzerland, 2001.
2. Lee, S.; McCann, D.; Messenger, J.C. Working Time Around the World. Trend in Working Hours, Laws and Policies in a Global Comparative Perspective; International Labour Office: Geneva, Switzerland, 2007.
3. 1.American Federation of Teachers. (2017). 2017 Educator Quality of Work Life.
4. 2. Cox, A., Solomon, B., & Parris, D. (2018, May 8). Teacher well-being is a critical and often overlooked part of school health. <https://www.childtrends.org/blog/teacher-well-being-is-a-critical-and-often-overlooked-part-of-school-health>.
5. Grosch, J.W.; Caruso, C.C.; Rosa, R.R.; Sauter, S.L. Long hours of work in the US: Associations with demographic and organizational characteristics, psychosocial working conditions, and health. Am. J. Ind. Med. 2006,49, 943–952. [CrossRef]

